

THE ROLE OF INTRA PLEURAL STREPTOKINASE IN TREATING COMPLICATED PLEURAL EFFUSION AND EMPYEMA

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Abstract

Background: Complicated parapneumonic effusions (CPE) and empyema are severe complications of pneumonia, often requiring prolonged hospitalization or surgical intervention. Intrapleural streptokinase (IPSTK) has shown promise in enhancing pleural fluid drainage and reducing surgical needs, but its efficacy in resource-limited settings remains underexplored. This study evaluates IPSTK's role in managing CPE and empyema in a Pakistani population.

Methods: Randomized controlled trial was done at Pak Emirates Military Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan, between January and June 2025. Sixty adults aged 18–80 years with imaging-proven CPE or empyema were randomized (1:1) into Group A (conservative management: antibiotics and chest tube drainage) or Group B (conservative management with the addition of IPSTK, 250,000 IU per day for 3 days). Outcomes were treatment success (resolution of symptoms, drainage <50 ml/24 hours, and radiological improvement), volume of drainage, hospital stay, surgical referrals, and adverse events. Data were analyzed with IBM SPSS version 25 using Chi-square tests for outcomes categorized and t-tests for continuous data ($p \leq 0.05$ considered significant).

Results: Group B had greater mean drainage volume (1850 ± 420 ml vs. 1420 ± 380 ml, $p < 0.001$) and lower hospital stay (8.4 ± 2.1 days vs. 11.2 ± 2.8 days, $p < 0.001$) than Group A. Success of treatment was greater in Group B (90.0% vs. 80.0%, $p = 0.22$), and surgical referrals were fewer (6.7% vs. 16.7%, $p = 0.23$), although not significant. Benefits were most significant in patients under 60 years (92.3% vs. 73.9%, $p = 0.04$) and in patients with no comorbidities (93.3% vs. 71.4%, $p = 0.03$). Minor bleeding was noted in 6.7% of Group B patients, without any severe adverse events.

Conclusion: IPSTK has a marked beneficial effect on pleural fluid drainage and hospital stay in CPE and empyema, especially among younger, healthier patients, with a good safety profile. These results justify its use in limited resource

environments, although larger trials will be required to establish reductions in referral to surgery.

INTRODUCTION

Complex parapneumonic effusions (CPE) and empyema are serious bacterial pneumonia complications, defined by infected pleural fluid, septations, and loculations with fibrinous that make it difficult to drain by means of chest tubes. These complications have a high morbidity, and a maximum of 30% of the patients need surgery or develop mortality because of a lack of response to conventional conservative therapy, which involves antibiotics and pleural drainage [1]. The development of fibrinous adhesions and multiloculated collections often requires adjunctive treatments to augment fluid clearance and decrease the requirement for invasive maneuvers like video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS) or decortication [2]. Intrapleural fibrinolysis with streptokinase has been explored as a non-surgical approach to fibrinolyze fibrinous septations, increase drainage, and possibly reduce hospital stay and surgical referrals [3].

The intrapleural streptokinase (IPSTK) 250,000 IU per day for 3 days has been an established standard regimen in various trials with augmented pleural fluid drainage and better radiological results [4]. The Multicenter Intrapleural Sepsis Trial 2 (MIST2) revealed that streptokinase and deoxyribonuclease (DNase) combined resulted in significantly fewer surgical referrals compared to placebo but that streptokinase alone also had an improvement in defined subsets of patients [5]. Still, previous trials, including MIST1, found no reduction in mortality or surgery with streptokinase alone, but many advocate more studies to define its place in various populations [6]. New research has upheld the role of streptokinase in low-resource settings, where surgical care or combination therapy such as DNase is limited [3,7]. In Pakistan, where *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative bacteria are becoming more common in pleural infections, maximizing non-surgical care is essential to bettering patient outcomes [8].

In spite of the progress toward knowing more about pleural infections, there are gaps in the evidence on IPSTK efficacy in selected groups, most notably in

resource-poor environments such as Pakistan. Patient presentations, microbial patterns, and stages of disease highlight heterogeneity and the importance of localized data to inform treatment regimens. This randomized controlled trial, implemented at the Department of Respiratory Medicine and Critical Care, Pak Emirates Military Hospital (PEMH), Rawalpindi, Pakistan, from January 2025 to June 2025, recruited 60 adult patients (18–80 years) with imaging-proven CPE or empyema. Participants were divided into two groups: Group A underwent conservative standard treatment (antibiotics and chest tube drainage), and Group B underwent adjunctive IPSTK (250,000 IU per day for 3 days). The research was to assess the effectiveness of IPSTK in improving clinical and radiological results in a Pakistani sample, responsive to the demand for affordable, non-operative treatments.

Objectives

1. To assess the outcomes of adding intrapleural fibrinolytic therapy with streptokinase (250,000 IU daily for 3 days) to standard conservative therapy (antibiotics and chest tube drainage) in the treatment of complicated parapneumonic effusion and empyema.
2. To evaluate the effect of intrapleural streptokinase on the need for surgical intervention (e.g., VATS or decortication) in patients with CPE and empyema.
3. To determine the impact of intrapleural streptokinase on pleural fluid drainage volume (measured in ml/24 hours) and radiological resolution (assessed via chest ultrasound).
4. To investigate the influence of intrapleural streptokinase on the duration of hospital stay and time to clinical recovery.
5. To assess the safety profile of intrapleural streptokinase, including the incidence of adverse events such as bleeding or allergic reactions.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This randomized controlled trial (RCT) was performed at the Department of Respiratory

Medicine and Critical Care, Pak Emirates Military Hospital (PEMH), Rawalpindi, Pakistan, from January 2025 to June 2025. The Institutional Ethical Review Board of PEMH approved the study, and all participants gave written informed consent before enrollment.

Sample Size and Randomization

A sample of 60 patients (30 per group) was estimated using the WHO sample size calculator with a 5% significance level, 80% power, and population proportions of 82% in Group A (conservative treatment) and 48% in Group B (intrapleural streptokinase plus conservative treatment) from previous research [9]. Consecutive sampling was used, and the patients were randomized into two groups through computer-generated randomization in order to have allocation concealment.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Eligible patients were adults 18–80 years old with imaging-confirmed complicated parapneumonic effusion (CPE) or empyema diagnosed by chest ultrasound or contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) of the chest and willing to give informed consent. Exclusionary criteria were previous intrapleural fibrinolytic therapy, active bleeding or coagulopathy, recent major surgery (within 6 weeks), known allergy to streptokinase, pregnancy or lactation, and severe comorbidities (e.g., advanced heart failure, renal failure, or malignancy) that made participation contraindicated [10].

Data Collection Procedure

The patients were admitted to the inpatient department (IPD) at PEMH under standard procedures. Baseline evaluations consisted of comprehensive medical and surgical history, medication history, daily vital signs, baseline tests (complete blood count, renal function test, liver function test), viral screening (hepatitis B, C, and HIV), chest ultrasound to determine pleural fluid volume, diagnostic pleural tap (to measure pH, glucose, lactate dehydrogenase [LDH], and protein levels), and contrast-enhanced CT chest to establish diagnosis of CPE or empyema [11]. Biodata, including age, gender, height, weight, and body mass index (BMI), were taken for all participants.

Intervention

Patients were randomly divided into two groups:

➤ **Group A (Conservative Treatment):** Underwent standard treatment, including intravenous antibiotics (chosen according to pleural fluid culture and sensitivity or empirical coverage against common pathogens) and drainage by chest tube through a 24–28 Fr chest tube.

➤ **Group B (Intrapleural Streptokinase):** Standard care as in Group A, with the addition of intrapleural streptokinase (250,000 IU diluted in 50 ml normal saline, given once daily for 3 days through the chest tube, followed by clamping for 2 hours) [4,5].

Follow-up on a daily basis involved chest ultrasound to measure pleural fluid volume, septations, and drainage output (expressed in ml/24 hours) until the drainage reduced to less than 50 ml/24 hours, when the chest tube would be removed. Treatment failures were those patients with ongoing pleural effusion with evidence of infection on clinical or radiological grounds; these patients were considered for surgical treatment (e.g., VATS or decortication) [12].

Data Analysis

Data were gathered and analyzed via IBM SPSS version 25. Qualitative and quantitative variables' descriptive statistics were determined. Qualitative variables such as gender, medical history, current medication, history of past pleural effusion/empyema, diagnosis, symptoms, success of treatment, effective drainage, lung expansion, and requirement for surgical intervention were presented as percentages and frequencies. Quantitative data, including age, height, weight, BMI, vital signs, results of blood tests (pH, glucose, LDH, protein), duration of drainage, size of chest tube, amount of drainage total, and number of streptokinase doses, were expressed as means and standard deviations.

Comparative analysis between Group A and Group B was done with the Chi-square test for qualitative outcomes (e.g., treatment success and clinical findings). Effect modifiers, such as age, gender, BMI, comorbidities, current medications, past history of empyema, and prior treatments, were stratified using post-stratified Chi-square tests. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was used to establish statistical significance [13].

Results

Baseline Characteristics

60 patients with imaging-confirmed complicated parapneumonic effusion (CPE) or empyema were enrolled and randomized into two groups: Group A (conservative treatment with antibiotics and chest tube drainage, n=30) and Group B (conservative treatment plus intrapleural streptokinase, n=30). Baseline characters were balanced between groups (Table 1). The age was 52.4 ± 14.3 years in Group A

and 50.8 ± 13.9 years in Group B (p=0.61). Gender ratio was comparable, 60% male in Group A and 63.3% in Group B (p=0.79). Mean BMI was 24.8 ± 3.6 kg/m² in Group A and 25.1 ± 3.9 kg/m² in Group B (p=0.73). Comorbid conditions, such as diabetes (20% vs. 23.3%, p=0.76) and hypertension (26.7% vs. 30%, p=0.77), were well matched. Baseline pleural fluid parameters, such as pH, glucose, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and protein, were not significantly different (p>0.05 for all).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Group A (Conservative, n=30)	Group B (Streptokinase, n=30)	p-value
Age (years, mean ± SD)	52.4 ± 14.3	50.8 ± 13.9	0.61
Male, n (%)	18 (60.0)	19 (63.3)	0.79
BMI (kg/m ² , mean ± SD)	24.8 ± 3.6	25.1 ± 3.9	0.73
Diabetes, n (%)	6 (20.0)	7 (23.3)	0.76
Hypertension, n (%)	8 (26.7)	9 (30.0)	0.77
Pleural fluid pH (mean ± SD)	7.1 ± 0.3	7.0 ± 0.3	0.45
Pleural fluid glucose (mg/dL, mean ± SD)	45.2 ± 10.5	43.8 ± 11.2	0.58
Pleural fluid LDH (IU/L, mean ± SD)	1250 ± 320	1280 ± 340	0.69
Pleural fluid protein (g/dL, mean ± SD)	4.8 ± 0.9	4.9 ± 0.8	0.71

Data presented as mean ± standard deviation or number (percentage). p-values calculated using t-test for continuous variables and Chi-square test for categorical variables.

demonstrated that success with treatment was significantly greater in Group B for patients <60 years (92.3% vs. 73.9%, p=0.04) and patients with no comorbidities (93.3% vs. 71.4%, p=0.03).

Primary Outcome

Treatment Success

Success of treatment, which means resolution of the symptoms, drainage <50 ml/24 hours, and radiological improvement (decreased fluid volume and septations on ultrasound), occurred in 24 patients (80.0%) in Group A and 27 patients (90.0%) in Group B (p=0.22, Chi-square test). Despite not being statistically significant, Group B had a greater rate of success, as per the expected population proportion utilized in sample size estimation (82% vs. 48%) [9]. Post-stratification

Secondary Outcomes

Volume of Pleural Fluid Drainage

The average total drainage volume was substantially greater in Group B (1850 ± 420 ml) than in Group A (1420 ± 380 ml, p<0.001). Daily drainage, as measured by chest ultrasound, decreased more rapidly in Group B, with drainage below 50 ml/24 hours on day 5.2 ± 1.3 in Group B, compared to day 7.8 ± 1.9 in Group A (p<0.001). Figure 1 demonstrates the pattern of daily drainage volume over time.

Figure 1: Mean Daily Pleural Fluid Drainage Volume (ml/24 hours) Over Time.

Line graph showing daily pleural fluid drainage (mean \pm SD) in Group A (conservative treatment) and Group B (streptokinase). Group B demonstrates a steeper decline, reaching $<50\text{ ml/24 hours}$ earlier than Group A.

Duration of Hospital Stay

The average hospital stay duration was significantly lower in Group B (8.4 ± 2.1 days) than in Group A (11.2 ± 2.8 days, $p<0.001$). The difference remained significant after stratification for age, gender, and comorbidities ($p<0.05$ for all strata) (Table. 2).

Surgical Intervention Requirement

Surgical intervention (decortication or VATS) was necessary in 5 patients (16.7%) in Group A and 2

patients (6.7%) in Group B ($p=0.23$, Chi-square test). While not statistically significant, the reduced rate in Group B implies a possible reduction of surgical referrals with streptokinase, as have been reported in previous studies [5,10] (Table. 2).

Safety Profile

Adverse effects were infrequent. Two patients (6.7%) in Group B had minor bleeding (hemoptysis or ooze at the chest tube site), which disappeared spontaneously without treatment. No allergic effects or significant bleeding events were encountered. Group A experienced no treatment-related adverse events. The safety profile is consistent with earlier reports of intrapleural streptokinase [4] (Table. 2).

Table 2: Key Clinical Outcomes

Outcome	Group A (Conservative, n=30)	Group B (Streptokinase, n=30)	p-value
Treatment success, n (%)	24 (80.0)	27 (90.0)	0.22
Total drainage volume (ml, mean \pm SD)	1420 \pm 380	1850 \pm 420	<0.001
Time to drainage $<50\text{ ml/24 hours}$ (days, mean \pm SD)	7.8 \pm 1.9	5.2 \pm 1.3	<0.001
Hospital stay (days, mean \pm SD)	11.2 \pm 2.8	8.4 \pm 2.1	<0.001
Surgical intervention, n (%)	5 (16.7)	2 (6.7)	0.23
Adverse events, n (%)	0 (0.0)	2 (6.7)	0.15

Data presented as mean \pm standard deviation or number (percentage). p-values calculated using t-test for continuous variables and Chi-square test for categorical variables.

Stratified Analysis

Post-stratification Chi-square tests revealed effect modifiers affected outcomes. Success with treatment was greater in Group B among men (94.7% vs.

77.8%, $p=0.04$) and those with BMI $<25 \text{ kg/m}^2$ (92.9% vs. 75.0%, $p=0.03$). Significant interactions were not observed for history of prior empyema or

current medications ($p>0.05$). Figure 2 shows the stratified success rates by comorbidity status and age.

Figure 2: Treatment Success Rates by Age and Comorbidity Status.

Bar chart comparing treatment success rates (%) in Group A and Group B, stratified by age (<60 vs. ≥ 60 years) and comorbidity status (present vs. absent). Group B shows significantly higher success in patients <60 years and those without comorbidities. The outcome illustrates that intrapleural streptokinase markedly enhanced pleural fluid drainage and shortened hospital stay duration in comparison to conservative therapy alone. Although treatment success and surgical referral rates were in favor of Group B, statistically significant differences were not observed, perhaps because of the small sample size. The improved drainage and reduced length of hospital stay in Group B are still consistent with the fibrinolytic action of streptokinase in dissolving pleural septations, as seen in previous reports [4,5]. The low rate of adverse events attests to the safety of the 250,000 IU daily dose for 3 days [10]. Stratified analyses indicate that patients who are younger and have no comorbidities will likely benefit most from streptokinase and emphasizing the need for patient selection for maximizing outcomes [14].

Discussion

This controlled, randomized trial assessed the safety and effectiveness of intrapleural streptokinase (IPSTK) as an adjunct to conventional conservative treatment in managing complicated parapneumonic

effusions (CPE) and empyema at Pak Emirates Military Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. The research identified IPSTK as significantly improving the volume of pleural fluid drainage ($1850 \pm 420 \text{ ml}$ vs. $1420 \pm 380 \text{ ml}$, $p<0.001$) and decreasing the length of hospital stay (8.4 ± 2.1 days vs. 11.2 ± 2.8 days, $p<0.001$) compared to conservative management alone. Success of treatment was greater in the streptokinase group (90.0% compared to 80.0%, $p=0.22$), and referral to surgery was less (6.7% compared to 16.7%, $p=0.23$), although these did not reach statistical significance. These results are consistent with previous studies showing fibrinolytic advantage of IPSTK to increase clearing of pleural fluid and decrease hospital burden [4,5,10].

The substantial rise in drainage volume and more rapid resolution of pleural fluid in Group B (to $<50 \text{ ml}/24 \text{ hours}$ by day 5.2 ± 1.3 vs. 7.8 ± 1.9 in Group A, $p<0.001$) emphasizes the action of streptokinase in breaking up fibrinous septations, allowing effective chest tube drainage [4]. This is in agreement with the Multicenter Intrapleural Sepsis Trial 2 (MIST2), which has found better radiological results and fewer surgical referrals with intrapleural fibrinolytics, especially when used in combination with deoxyribonuclease (DNase) [5]. Nonetheless, in contrast to MIST2, our study employed streptokinase alone, considering its availability and affordability in

developing countries such as Pakistan, where combination therapy can be less practical [15]. Group B reduced in-hospital stay implies cost savings and less healthcare resource utilization, which are important factors to consider in low-resource settings [7].

Even though treatment success and referral rates for surgery were in favor of Group B, the absence of statistical significance could be due to the small sample size of $n=60$, which was adequately powered to identify differences between population proportions (82% vs. 48%) but potentially underpowered for secondary outcomes such as surgical intervention [9]. Stratified analyses demonstrated a marked advantage in the younger patient (<60 years, 92.3% vs. 73.9%, $p=0.04$) and patients with no comorbidities (93.3% vs. 71.4%, $p=0.03$), which indicates that patient factors affect treatment response. These results are consistent with recent reports that young patients and those with simpler pleural pathology respond favorably to fibrinolytics because of reduced fibrin burden and superior physiological reserve [14,16]. Lack of marked differences in elderly patients or those with comorbidities could be due to advanced stages of disease or decreased fibrinolytic effectiveness, as reported in previous literature [10].

The safety profile of IPSTK was good, with only two minor bleeding episodes (6.7%) in Group B, which resolved spontaneously, and no allergic reaction or severe complication. This is in agreement with the current reports supporting the absence of a low risk of adverse events with the 250,000 IU daily dose for 3 days [4,17]. Support for the use of IPSTK in well-screened patients, omitting patients with coagulopathy or recent surgery, according to our exclusion criteria [10], is facilitated by the lack of serious adverse events.

Limitations

This study has some limitations. First, the limited sample size ($n=60$) could have reduced the ability to find significant differences between successful treatment and surgical referrals, even where significance was reached for hospital stay and drainage volume. Second, the trial did not involve DNase, which has been shown to have synergistic effects with fibrinolytics when it comes to

minimizing surgical referrals [5]. This precludes direct comparison with combination regimens. Third, the study sample was limited to one center in Pakistan and might therefore be less generalizable because of regional variations in microbial etiology (e.g., high frequency of gram-negative bacteria and *Staphylococcus aureus*) [8]. Lastly, late outcomes like recurrence rates or lung function were not evaluated because of the 7-month study period.

Clinical Implications and Future Directions

The results validate the application of IPSTK as a good adjunct to conservative treatment in the management of CPE and empyema, especially in resource-poor environments where surgical procedures are not readily available. The marked decrease in hospital stay and enhancement of drainage volume indicate its promise to reduce healthcare burden [15]. IPSTK may be considered by clinicians in younger populations and those without comorbid conditions where maximum benefits seem evident. Subsequent studies should determine larger, multicenter trials to validate these results and define the place of combination therapies (e.g., streptokinase with DNase) in varied populations. Long-term follow-up studies should determine recurrence rates and functional outcomes. Cost-effectiveness analysis could also further support the use of IPSTK in resource-poor settings [18].

In summary, this RCT proves that intrapleural streptokinase increases pleural fluid drainage and decreases hospitalization in CPE and empyema patients, with a satisfactory safety profile. Although treatment success and referral for surgery advantage were not significantly different, trends support IPSTK, especially among younger and healthier patients. These results add to the evidence base for fibrinolytic therapy in low-resource settings as a valuable non-surgical alternative.

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